

Relationship Between Entropy and Energy Densities in Quantum Mechanics

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In classical statistical mechanics, $C \exp[-(mv^2/2 + V(x))/T]$ represents density i.e. the probability for a particle to have a velocity v and be at x . If applies this probability to Shannon's entropy formula, one obtains $C/T (mv^2/2 + V(x)) \exp[-(mv^2/2 + V(x))/T] + \exp[-(mv^2/2 + V(x))/T] \ln(C)$. Thus, it seems energy times density + density times $\ln(C)$ is the entropy density, a well known result in classical statistical mechanics, although sometimes not explicitly stated. The first term integrated over x is essentially the kinetic energy, while the second integrated over velocity yields the potential energy term. Thus, the first term partial density seems to be a purely momentum dependent kinetic energy piece times probability and the second a purely x dependent potential energy piece. (There is still an integral over velocity for the first term and one over x for the second to obtain the full entropy.)

In quantum mechanics, we argue that $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$ serves as the probability where $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) = \text{wavefunction}$. This leads to an expression for entropy density with two terms, one of which may be immediately integrated over momentum and the other over space. If one wishes to make a link to the classical statistical mechanical case, one may ask what requirement is necessary for the momentum related piece to represent average kinetic energy and the spatial part, average potential energy. The requirement, we find, yields the wavefunction of the ground state harmonic oscillator. For other cases, the partial density is not equivalent to average energy. Thus, we try to establish a link between entropy density and energy density, but require the kinetic energy related term to be strictly a function of momentum and the potential related term strictly one of x .

In quantum mechanics, one may form averages at a point x . For example, $KE_{ave}(x) = [\text{Sum over } p p^2/2m a(p) \exp(ipx)]/W(x)$. If one examines a $p/-p$ pair with $a(p)=a(-p)$ (for example), $\cos(px)$ terms arise which are positive at some x and negative at others. We argued in previous notes that this represents stochastic flow in the opposite direction from that expected by $-dV/dx$. In other words, $-dV/dx$ is an average which consists of stochastic force addends which may give momentum hits to the right or left, but which add to yield $-dV/dx$. As a result, one may have negative contributions to the kinetic energy (and density as well). In this note, we argue one may also have negative contributions to the entropy density due to this phenomenon.

Quantum Mechanical Entropy

We argue that:

$$\text{Probability} = a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x) \quad ((1))$$

should be used to calculate Shannon's quantum entropy. This probability appears in the expression for spatial density: $W^*(x)W(x) = \text{Sum over } p_1, p_2 a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$ and so we think it represents the full microscopic detail. $W^*(x)W(x)$ and even $W(x)$ are ensemble

averages and we argue against forming an entropy expression using any averages. The probability $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2 x)$ is equivalent to: $P(p_1/x)P(p_2/x)P(x)$. In previous notes, we considered $P(p/x)P(x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x)$. In this note, we argue against this probability because $W(x)$ is an ensemble average i.e. equivalent to: $\text{Sum over } p \ a(p) \exp(ipx)$. We wish to remove all ensemble averages from the probability used in Shannon's entropy. In such a case, the entropy density becomes:

$$\text{Shannon's Entropy density} = - \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \ln[a(p) \exp(ipx)] + \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \ln \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx) \quad ((2))$$

At this point, we wish to point out a peculiar feature of this entropy which is also found in various other averages, such as spatial density and kinetic energy at x (in quantum mechanics). This is the feature of negative contributions from $p/-p$ pairs to an average which is strictly positive. For example, spatial density or average kinetic energy at x must be positive. Both, however, are created, we argue, by microscopic behaviour related to complex probabilities $a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$. In the case of spatial density, $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x)a(p_2)\exp(ip_2 x)$ is the product of relative probabilities for a p_1 at x which is changed into p_2 by a stochastic force hit. For kinetic energy, one uses $[\text{Sum over } p \ p^2/2m \ a(p) \exp(ipx)]/W(x)$. If one considers $p/-p$ pairs and assumes $a(p)=a(-p)$, for example, one obtains $\cos(px)$ terms which are positive at some x and negative at others. In previous notes, we argued the negative probability represents flow opposite to that expected by the average $-dV/dx$. In other words, if one has a set of particles moving to the right and one particle receives a stochastic hit to the left, it is as if one loses particles and kinetic energy. ((2)) seems to suggest this same feature is present in Shannon's entropy. Thus, ((2)) represents a kind of ensemble averaged entropy with microscopic motion which both contributes and removes entropy from different x points.

This is curious because Shannon's entropy follows from the counting of arrangements with probabilities for different observables. For example, consider a coin toss which may yield heads or tails. There is $P(\text{heads})$ and $P(\text{tails})$ i.e. a probability for each observable. If one tosses the coin many times, the overall probability should be: $P(\text{heads})^{N(\text{heads})}P(\text{tails})^{N(\text{tails})}$ or $1/[\text{number of arrangements}]$.

Taking the log of the first term yields Shannon's entropy. To calculate the number of arrangements, one may use:

$$N! / [(N(\text{heads}))! (N(\text{tails}))!] \quad ((3)), \text{ take the log and use Stirling's approximation.}$$

For the quantum case, there are three observables, p , x and the sign of the probability (from $\cos(px)$ if one considers $p/-p$ pairs. The sign, however, is not stochastic, it follows from p and x . If $\cos(px)$ is negative, however, one loses density and kinetic energy at x and it seems one loses entropy as well. This seems to follow from the fact that if one removes a particle from a system, entropy will drop if other variables are not changed. Thus, the quantum entropy situation is curious.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

In classical statistical mechanics, density or probability is given by:

$$f(e) = C \exp(- (.5mv^2 + V(x))/T) \quad ((4))$$

This density seems to be driven by balanced two body reactions i.e.:

$$f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4) \text{ where } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \text{ and } e=p^2/2m \quad ((5))$$

Thus, p or velocity is the driver, but if there is v at x (where say $V(x)=0$), then at x_1 $v_1^2/2m + V(x) = v^2/2m$. Thus, full energy is used in the exponent in ((4)). If ((4)) is used in Shannon's entropy:

$$\text{Entropy density} = [-\ln(C) + .5mv^2 + V(x)]/T f(e) \quad ((5))$$

Thus, there is strong connection with energy (as known in the literature) but one should note that $.5mv^2$ only depends on velocity and $V(x)$ on x. Thus, for $.5mv^2$ $f(e)$ one may integrate out x and for $V(x)f(e)$ one may integrate out x. (Both terms have x and p integrals and one performs one of these integrals for each.) This leads to a partial entropy density closely related to energy.

In the next section, we consider the analogous partial entropy density for the quantum case and see under which conditions it matches the classical one i.e. one closely related to energy.

Quantum Entropy Density and Energy

If one integrates the first entropy density term of ((2)) over p and the second over x, one obtains:

$$\text{Entropy} = b \sum_{p} a(p)a(-p) \ln[a(p)a(-p)] + \int dx \frac{1}{2} W(x) x \frac{d}{dx} W(x) \quad ((6))$$

Here b is a normalization constant linked to the basis function $\exp(ipx)$.

For the first term of ((6)) to represent kinetic energy, a solution is $a(p)=a(-p)$ and $a(p)=b_1 p^2$ where b_1 is a constant. Thus, $a(p)= C_1 \exp(-b_1 p^2)$. This automatically yields the solution for $W(x)= \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx)$. It is known that the Fourier transform of a Gaussian is a Gaussian, so $W(x)=C_2 \exp(-b_2 x^2)$. Thus, the second term of ((6)) is proportional to $x^2 W(x)W(x)$ which is very similar to the potential energy.

Thus, for one solution, namely the quantum ground state solution of an oscillator, one has partial quantum entropy density match the classical partial entropy density. It should still be noted that microscopically the quantum case differs from the classical with the quantum case having negative entropy density contributions from p/-p pairs. For other situations, the two terms in the entropy density expression no longer match kinetic and potential energy and one leaves

the “average” classical statistical mechanical situation represented by the ground state of the oscillator.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in the classical case, entropy density is strongly connected to kinetic energy plus potential energy (with the first being written solely in terms of v and the latter in terms of x), differing by $\{\ln(C)\}f(e)$ where C is the normalization constant of $f(e)$. This is well known in classical statistical mechanics. Here $f(e) = C \exp(- (mv^2/2 + V(x))/T)$. From $-f(e)\ln(f(e))$, one term is related to $mv^2/2 \exp(-mv^2/2T)$ with no x present (if one integrates out x). This term is directly related to average kinetic energy. The other term is related to potential energy and x only if one integrates out v .

In the quantum case, we argue that the probability to use in Shannon’s entropy expression is: $a(p_1)\exp(ip_1 x) a(p_2) \exp(ip_2 x)$. This leads to two terms. The first may be integrated over x and the second over p . If the first term is to represent average kinetic energy proportional to \sum over p $p^2/2m a(p)a(p)$, and the second, average potential energy: $\int dx W(x) W(x)V(x)$ (1 dimension), then only the ground state quantum oscillator solution will yield this result.

We also note that in the computation of the “ensemble” entropy density, there may be negative entropy contributions from $p/-p$ pairs just as in the case of spatial density and average kinetic energy.